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Book of Abstracts

Breakthrough curves of per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and pharmaceuticals using activated carbon

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are long-lasting chemicals. Their presence is harmful due to their toxicity and bioaccumulation. High exposure to these compounds increases the risk of dangerous health issues for humans and environmental contamination [1]. Besides, pharmaceutical compounds are contaminants of emerging concern since they are continuously discharged into the environment, becoming a long-term problem for human health and the environment [2]. Activated carbons (ACs), prepared from different biomass sources, are efficient and versatile biomaterials for PFAS pollutant removal. In order to implement adsorption processes at an industrial scale, this study involved the selection of 3 PFAS (perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA) and perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)) and 3 pharmaceuticals (diclofenac (DCF), valsartan (VAL) and iopromide (IOP)) to evaluate their performance on fixed-bed columns using specific activated carbon synthesised from biomass. Their breakthrough curves were determined, and the results were compared with commercial activated carbon. The tests were performed on synthetic water matrices and real water samples from a wastewater treatment plant effluent.

References

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2. Nazari, G.; Abolghasemi, H.; Esmaili, M.; Sadeghi Pouya, E. *Appl Surf Sci* 2016, 375.